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Cardiovascular Risks in Pregnancy 2024: Digital Solutions

(With A Little Help From My Friends)

Abstract | Abstract

Keywords

Cardiovascular risk stratification in pregnancy • Healthcare kiosk • Obstetric networks • Hypertensive diseases in pregnancy • CHAP Study • Molecular genetics prior to pregnancy

Conflicts of interest: K.J.G. Schmailzl: no conflicts of interest.

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Pregnancy 1: Risk assessment today

1.1 Is my pregnant patient at risk for cardiovascular complications?

Morbidity and mortality in pregnancy - unlike in the days of "puerperal fever" - are determined by cardiovascular complications; the most common cause of death in pregnancy and the puerperium in developed countries of the so-called First and Second Worlds is pulmonary artery embolism, and hypertensive diseases are responsible for a large proportion of morbidity.

Therefore, it seems reasonable to assess the cardiovascular risk at the beginning of a pregnancy.

Pregnancy and the puerperium are associated with major cardio-circulatory changes. For example, circulating plasma volume increases the volume to be pumped by the heart by 40- 50% per time; in parallel, resting heart rate increases by around 10-15%. Against this background, the European Society of Cardiology guidelines for the management of cardiovascular disease in pregnancy [ESC 2018] recommend risk assessment and counselling for all women with a known or suspected congenital or acquired cardiovascular (incl. aortic) disease who want to become (or are) pregnant.

Risk assessment and counselling aim to make necessary decisions based on provable information, to change or adjust medications that require consideration of special features in pregnancy in a timely manner, and to plan care for the entire further course of pregnancy in terms of location, time and content.

The 2018 guidelines, in contrast to previous statements, emphasise that special attention should be paid to risks that could arise from assisted reproductive techniques. Also new is that in the case of a high risk or possible contraindications to pregnancy, recommendations for contraception should be explained and the pros and cons of terminating a pregnancy for reasons of severe cardiovascular disease should be discussed with the woman.

Compared to the 2011 guidelines, which only emphasized the importance of a structured risk assessment, a full risk assessment using the mWHO classification is now recommended for every woman with heart disease of childbearing age prior to pregnancy (recommendation grade I, evidence level C).

The mWHO classification (*modified World Health Organization classification of maternal cardiovascular risk*) is an expert system that combines disease-specific

information and other risk predictors (mWHO I-IV).

	Diagnosis (if otherwise healthy)
mWHO I	Mild pulmonary stenosis, ductus botalli (DAP) or mitral valve prolapse (MKP) Successfully repaired simple lesions (ASD, VSD, DAP, mal-orifice pulmonary veins). Clustered isolated SVES/VES
mWHO II	Uncorrected ASD/VSD Operated tetralogy of Fallot Turner syndrome without aortic aneurysm Majority of all supraventricular arrhythmias
mWHO II-III	Left ventricular pump function (LV-EF) 0.45-0.55 Hypertrophic cardiomyopathy (HCM) Valvular heart disease (not mWHO I or IV) Marfan's or other hereditary connective tissue disorders involving the ao. thor. (HTAD) without aneurysm Aorta <45 mm with bicuspid aortic valve Corrected aortic coarctation (CoA) ASD
mWHO III	Left ventricular pump function (LV-EF) 0.30-0.45 Previous peripartum cardiomyopathy (PPCM) without residual pump function impairment "Mechanical" artificial heart valve Systemic right ventricle with good/only slightly reduced pump function Fontan circuit (if otherwise healthy and free of complications). Uncorrected cyanotic heart defect and other complex heart diseases Moderate mitral stenosis Severe asymptomatic aortic stenosis Moderate aortic dilatation [40-45 mm in HTADs; 45-50 mm in bicuspid aortic valve, <i>aortic size index</i> (ASI) 20-25 mm/m ²) in Turner syndrome, <50 mm in tetralogy of Fallot]. Ventricular tachycardia

mWHO IV	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Left ventricular pump function (LV-EF) <0.30 or NYHA class III-IV Pulmonary arterial hypertension (PH) Previous peripartum cardiomyopathy (PPCM) with residual restriction of left ventricular pump function Severe mitral stenosis Severe symptomatic aortic stenosis Systemic right ventricle with moderately-highly impaired pump function Severe aortic dilatation (>45 mm in Marfan syndrome or other HTAD, >50 mm in bicuspid aortic valve, ASI >25 mm/m² in Turner syndrome, >50 mm in tetralogy of Fallot, Ehlers-Danlos syndrome of the vascular type (vEDS)) Severe recurrent aortic coarctation Fontan circuit with any complication
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Tab. 1: Modified WHO classification of maternal cardiovascular risk [transcribed from: *The Task Force for the Management of Cardiovascular Diseases during Pregnancy of the European Society of Cardiology (ESC) 2018: p. 3175*].

ASI = aortic size index; LV-EF = left ventricular ejection fraction; HTAD = heritable thoracic aortic disease; mWHO = modified World Health Organization classification; NYHA = New York Heart Association; WHO = World Health Organization; DAP Ductus arteriosus persistens Botalli, MKP Mitral valve prolapse, ASD Atrial septal defect, VSD Ventricular septal defect, SVES Supraventricular extrasystole, VES Ventricular extrasystole, CoA Coarctatio aortae (Aortic isthmic stenosis, AIS), Ao. thor. Aorta thoracalis, HCM hypertrophic cardiomyopathy, PPCM peripartum cardiomyopathy, vEDS vascular type Ehlers-Danlos syndrome

Tab. 1 allows classification of whether a pregnant woman is a risk patient for cardiovascular complications and her risk level on the basis of a previously known or newly diagnosed cardiovascular disease.

	mWHO I	mWHO II	mWHO II-III	mWHO III	mWHO IV
Risk	No detectable increase in risk of maternal mortality and/or no or only slightly increased risk of morbidity	Slightly increased maternal mortality risk and/or moderately increased morbidity risk	Moderately increased maternal mortality risk and/or moderately- significantly increased morbidity risk.	Significantly increased maternal mortality risk and/or significantly increased morbidity risk	Extremely increased maternal mortality and/or morbidity risk
Frequency of serious cardiac events in the mother	2,5-5,0%	5,7-10,5%	10,0-19,0%	19,0-27,0%	40,0-100,0%
Consulting	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes: Expert advice!	Yes: Pregnancy contraindicated; if pregnancy has occurred, abortion worthy of discussion
Support	Local hospital	Local hospital	Reference clinic	Centre for Obstetrics and Cardiovascular Diseases	Centre for Obstetrics and Cardiovascular Diseases
Minimum follow-up	1-2	1/Trimester	Bi-monthly	Monthly or bi-monthly	Monthly
Place of delivery	Local hospital	Local hospital	Reference clinic	Centre for Obstetrics and Cardiovascular Diseases	Centre for Obstetrics and Cardiovascular Diseases

Tab. 2: Modified WHO classification of maternal cardiovascular risk [transcribed from: *The Task Force for the Management of*

Cardiovascular Diseases during Pregnancy of the European Society of Cardiology (ESC) 2018: p. 3175].

Table 2 enables decisions to be made on the basis of the risk grouping as to which action-guiding consequences can be derived from this.

1.2 Counselling needs and goals before the onset of pregnancy

In the case of pre-existing cardiovascular syndromes, there are a few (mWHO IV) for whom the risk of a life-threatening worsening due to pregnancy is high, and for whom pregnancy may need to be discouraged or even a termination discussed if pregnancy has already occurred. In up to 1/3 of documented maternal deaths in Germany, there was a known risk in the form of pre-existing conditions. There is a need for counselling - especially pre- conceptual - in all mWHO classes at least from mWHO II, in mWHO classes III and IV by "experts", i.e. - in a team with obstetricians - also cardiologists who are familiar with the corresponding clinical pictures. Since some of these are rare cardiovascular syndromes for which special consultations exist, it is not uncommon for these to be university outpatient clinics or particularly specialised practices. This "team building" is highly recommended from mWHO II-III onwards - at least if you want to avoid complications or, if complications have occurred, further entanglements.

1.3. Heart Team (*Pregnancy Heart Team*)

In these cases, according to the current guidelines, a "heart team" (*international: "Pregnancy Heart Team"*) should come together. Ideally, it consists of representatives from obstetrics, cardiology, possibly paediatric cardiology or cardiology for adults with congenital heart defects (EMAH), possibly angiology, anaesthesia and intensive care medicine, neonatology. Such constructions have already proven themselves in "cardiac medicine" and elsewhere:

e.g. in the indication and implementation of interventions in the border area of cardiology and cardiac surgery (e.g. in catheter-based heart valve interventions). Even if they are initially associated with more "paperwork", they promote a cross-disciplinary view and, if necessary, a change of perspective for the individual member. These structures have long been established in the "tumor conferences" in oncology.

1.4. Cardiovascular diagnostics in pregnancy [long-term ECG,

imaging procedures, invasive-interventional procedures (percutaneous vs. surgical)].

In principle, almost all cardiological-diagnostic and -interventional-surgical procedures can also be considered during pregnancy, provided the indication is justified. This also explicitly applies to invasive procedures with radiation exposure (which must be limited to the thorax and performed under maximum shielding of the abdominal cavity). It goes without saying that if such procedures are de facto indicated (these may be, for example, catheter-based heart valve interventions, ablations for malignant cardiac arrhythmias or even coronary angiography), the radiation exposure is minimized in terms of time and the procedure is

postponed to the last months of pregnancy if possible. Cardiosurgical procedures can almost always be avoided during pregnancy by catheter-based interventions; there have been successful examples of this for decades, especially in the area of valvular heart disease.

However, the focus of interest in a cardiovascular risk patient is the internal cardiological diagnosis, whether for the initial diagnosis or for follow-up. The most important role is played by ECG and long-term ECG as well as imaging procedures such as echocardiography and sonography and cardiovascular MR imaging. The latter has meanwhile developed into a gold standard in some cardiovascular questions, which the reimbursement practice of the statutory health insurance funds does not yet follow accordingly. Primary imaging, however, continues to be ultrasound diagnostics of the heart and supplementary sonographic procedures of the lungs and abdomen. In contrast to obstetric fine diagnostics, the focus is not on complete and detailed diagnostics, but on the "robust" determination of characteristic data such as the size of the four heart cavities, pumping function and valve functions. If imaging and image quality permit, at least two-thirds of all cardiovascular questions can be answered with such findings. Where imaging capability and image quality do not allow reliable conclusions, MR imaging with pre-formulated questions should be organised without long delays. The resting ECG is a standard diagnostic test, but the majority of the questions linked to it can only be answered by a long-term ECG. Today, "long-term" does not always mean a 24-hour recording; recordings over two, three and up to seven days are now possible. This makes perfect sense, as many cardiac arrhythmias only occur irregularly and at longer intervals.

Which diagnostic procedures have to be performed at which intervals in a cardiovascular risk patient is determined by the general risk stratification (cf. Tab. 1).

2. Traditional and digitally enhanced obstetric practice

We are used to organising the care of a pregnant woman on the basis of the "mother's passport" in the gynaecological-obstetric practice or, in case of impending complications, in a reference clinic. These forms of organisation will most likely be supplemented in the coming years by telemedical options (as is already partly realised in some countries - Denmark, Israel).

The digitally expanded obstetric practice may not be a sensible addition in the metropolis, but certainly in regions where care is scarce, mostly in rural areas. It saves travel and time. It is not yet clear which monitoring is really useful and effective to what extent, but both long-term ECG patches and ultrasound, as well as *point-of-care tests* ("from a drop of blood") can enable patient-oriented, customized follow-up. Their enforcement and dissemination depends on our will to have such facilitators available to women and caring physicians, partly on advances in applied research, in professional policy and last but not least in reimbursement and reimbursement practices of payers.

2.1 "Health kiosks" as part of obstetric networks?

What are called "health kiosks" in the current health policy discussion are new forms of organization for health care, along the entire care chain from preventive to reparative to rehabilitative medicine. Although these new forms of organization often integrate telemedical means and media, they are first and foremost an attempt to respond to situations that are precarious in terms of care: such as those that are increasingly manifesting themselves in rural regions, sparsely populated, characterized by rural exodus and ageing and the death of social infrastructure facilities that were once taken for granted, such as the rural doctor's practice or the small hospital. Partly mirroring these structural problems in the countryside are "problem districts" and social hotspots in metropolises, where access to health is problematic for some population groups: for reasons of intercultural differences and language

problems, lack of health education and competence, low incomes.

"Health kiosks", of which [Federal Ministry of Health:

[https://www.bundesgesundheitsministerium.de/service/begriffe-von-a-](https://www.bundesgesundheitsministerium.de/service/begriffe-von-a-z/g/gesundheitskiosk.html)

[z/g/gesundheitskiosk.html](https://www.bundesgesundheitsministerium.de/service/begriffe-von-a-z/g/gesundheitskiosk.html)] more than 1,000 are to be set up nationwide by the municipalities and financed by them and the health insurance companies, have quickly become the subject of controversial discussions. Depending on one's point of view, they are supposed to do more or less. Examples in other countries show how such "kiosks" or "health terminals" could provide low-threshold initial referrals and a kind of triaging or guidance system.

As a result of this and the increasing possibilities of e- and mHealth, which relies on new sensor technology and more generally "digital companions", the face and role of medical practice and outpatient clinics is likely to change - whether one welcomes it or not.

On the one hand, it will foreseeably become superfluous to visit a doctor's office at all for simple technical medical services such as an ECG or some parameters of clinical chemistry and microbiology: smartwatches and blood glucose self-measurements have been the pacesetters of this development.

On the other hand, in the majority of cases the results have to be classified by doctors, so that the practice and the outpatient clinic become more important *as communication partners*. This should only be possible if the lead hospital and practices are networked with community-established and operated "kiosks", thus ensuring care not only in the countryside and in socially disadvantaged areas again, but also lowering intersectoral barriers in the care chain as a result and increasing the overall quality of care.

2.2. "Medical Selfies?"

E. Topol, a US cardiologist, described in a post dated 30 November 2022 [Topol 2022] how he first plugged an ultrasound probe into his smartphone several years ago and curiously began taking pictures of his own body. Since his ultrasound experience had so far

been limited exclusively to the heart and echocardiography, he first searched Google for "How To" video clips to show the gall bladder or kidneys. After an hour, he had many images, and these medical selfies arranged themselves into his very own full-body ultrasound atlas.

The story does not end here, because a few months later he got severe

abdominal pain, took out his transducer again and discovered a congested kidney, went to the emergency room with the pictures and told the colleagues he thought he had colic because of a kidney stone. They sent him to CT anyway, which gave the same diagnosis.

This is an anecdote from what we may look back on as the first decade of digital medicine. And we all know that the monitoring of a pregnancy could be particularly suitable for such applications (be it the acquisition of ultrasound images or cardiotocographic findings, be it their remote transmission and integration into obstetric networks and reference centres). This can be illustrated by the example of Israel:

Pulsenmore 2023] not only developed a *point-of-care ultrasound* solution for "home" obstetric applications by connecting a transducer to a smartphone, but also connected it to a mobile app that guides the patient through a self-examination while establishing a teleconsultation with a clinician. The clinician sees the images via cloud storage on their dashboard and can talk to the patient online and assess the findings, which are then transferred to their electronic medical record.

The possible objections are obvious, but the advantages of such remote screening - immediate access to expert knowledge in complex cases, more comfort and involvement of the patient and her family, optimised resource management, higher productivity and accelerated processes - are likely to outweigh the disadvantages, at least for care- precarious regions, and the experience so far seems to confirm it.

Conclusion for daily practice

- Treatment of mild hypertension during pregnancy also promises benefits for the expectant mother (without endangering the child).
- In addition to the antihypertensives traditionally used in pregnancy, newer agents such as a- and b-blockers are also safe.

- Medical technology services such as ECG, blood pressure measurement, laboratory tests and simple ultrasound screens during pregnancy are possible via telemedicine for the benefit of the supervising doctor and patient.

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